

Study on Bimo Ceremony Music of Meigu Country of Yi Nationality in Liangshan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 29, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: March 30, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Bimo Ceremony ,Meigu County , Yi Nationality , Liangshan</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7786447</p>	<p><i>Ethnomusicology, in its study of the Bimo ritual music of the Liangshan Yi ethnic group, mainly constructs a cognitive scientific theory of Bimo ritual music from a methodological perspective, defining the scope of cognition as a form of Bimo ritual music distinct from other Yi ethnic regions, while the process of cognition mainly carries the dynamic process of the Bimo ritual music of the Liangshan Yi ethnic group, aiming to form a "cognitive ethnographic" theory based on The article will focus on the use of the ethnomusicologist Mei Mei's work, which is based on the theory of 'cognitive ethnography', to develop a dynamic musical cultural picture of the ritual music of the Yi people of Liangshan. The article will focus on the "hierarchical study of musical matters" proposed by the ethnomusicologist Metriam , a comprehensive analysis of the conceptual hierarchy of the ritual music of the Yi people of Liangshan, clarifying the attributes of this type of ritual music and the background culture rooted in the soil of Liangshan.</i></p>

Introduction

The theory of musicological analysis will have an important place in the text. The analysis of the musical forms of the Yi Yi rituals in Liangshan will focus on the joint role of music itself and its social and cultural environment, drawing on Professor Runyang's proposal that "musicological analysis is a higher level of professional analysis of a comprehensive nature" (see Yang Minkang: Music Morphological Analysis, Musicological Analysis and Ethnomusicological Analysis --A comparison of different methodological perspectives of traditional music studies and their cultural contexts[J]. (Music Art, 2014(3):69-79.), the research in this paper will focus more on the externalized forms of stylistic and aesthetic features in Yi Bi-mo ritual music, and use this as an entry point to reveal the social history of the Liangshan Yi people, form a value judgment of ritual music that presents the social reality, form a high-level cognitive research structure of Liangshan Yi Bi-mo ritual music, and unify Liangshan Yi Bi-mo ritual music The music of the Yi people in the Liangshan region is a high level cognitive research structure that unifies the form of Yi music and the cultural context behind the ritual. Thus, musicological analysis theory provides an important theoretical basis for the study of the ritual music of the Yi people of Liangshan.

Theory of the Chinese Religious Music Transmission System

This theory was first proposed by Professor Pu Hengqiang in a major pre-research project approved by Southwest University in 2012, entitled 'A Comprehensive, Systematic and In-depth Study of the Religious Music Transmission System in China' (The Theory of the Religious Music Transmission System in China), based on existing research results on religious music and relying on solid documentary analysis. This theory was first proposed by Professor Pu Hengqiang in his proposal for a major pre-research project on the heritage system of Chinese religious music, which was approved by Southwest University in 2012). This theory has implications for the methodology of this paper. This theory is an important guide to the research methodology of this paper. The comprehensive literature analysis of the ritual music of the Yi people in Liangshan was the basis for the preparation of the fieldwork, especially the concretization of the transmission vehicle and the guidance of the transmission method in the "Theory of Chinese Religious Music Transmission System", which provided a solid guarantee for the construction of a clear cultural system of religious music in this paper.

Definition Of Key Concepts

a. Ceremonial music

Ceremonial music is a subject area that has developed under the influence of the intersection of ritual and ethnomusicology. It refers primarily to the form of musical order for ceremonies. From ancient times to the present day, important occasions such as ancestral rituals, religious ceremonies and marriages and funerals have used music appropriate to the occasion to complete the ritual. For example, the national anthem is used on solemn occasions, and the march is used during military parades, all of which fall into the category of

ceremonial music. In ethnomusicology, the three main areas of study are Taoist ritual music, Buddhist ritual music and the music of folk beliefs.

b Yi Bi Mo

A bimo is a cleric in the traditional Yi religious rituals. In the Yi language, "Bi" means "chanting" and "Mo" means "elder" or "teacher", which literally means the elder who chants the scriptures during religious activities. It has been recorded since the time of the Three Kingdoms that a highly respected person with generations of family succession was called a "bimo", while a priest without rank or family succession was called a "suni". Apart from their family backgrounds, they are all clerics with important responsibilities in Yi religious rituals, but with differences in prestige and power. Legend has it that two of the most powerful priests are Biashira and Zeyadulpu.

c. Yi Bi-Mo Ritual Music

The ritual music of the Yi Bimo mainly includes the following: Mardudi (making the spirit sign), Sumi Bi (sending the spirit sign), Zimobi (reciting the peace sutra), Zhuo Ni Shuo (reciting the sutra of purifying the house), Xiu Bu (reciting the sutra of eliminating incantations), Sumi Na Gu (reciting the sutra of curing diseases), Li Ji Ri (reciting the sutra of cursing ghosts), Sumi Ri (reciting the sutra of cursing enemies) and so on. In addition to this, there is also a musical setting for the rituals of alliance and for the rituals of divine judgment in disputes.

d. Five States, Four Diameters, Three Lines

"The five states, four paths, and three lines" is the idea put forward by Professor Liu Zhengwei of the Wuhan Conservatory of Music in his article "The Genetic Gene of Music: Five States, Four Paths, and Three Lines of Traditional Music" in the Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music. He believes that there are genetic genes that have been passed down from generation to generation in ethnic folk music, and that the characteristics of these musical forms, which are made up of many specific elements, are in fact the genetic genes of folk music in various places, specifically influenced by the "historical, local, linguistic, mental and musical states". "The different influences of 'history, place, language, mind and music' have resulted in very different stylistic characteristics. In the three-dimensional research space of folk music, both vertically and horizontally, the north and south, the east and west of the north are the 'four paths', while the three dividing lines between the sister ethnic groups and the Han Chinese 'three lines', these three aspects form an orderly boarder dividing line of folk music characteristics. By grasping the principles of "five states, four paths and three lines", one can grasp the overall stylistic characteristics of Chinese folk music in general.

Research Implications

The Yi people are mainly found in the provinces of Yunnan, Guizhou and Sichuan. In this study, the group "Yi Meigu County Bimo" refers to the northern sub-dialect of Sichuan Yi "Meigu County", and Meigu is known as the "hometown of Bimo culture". This project is based on the study of the ritual music of the Yi people in Meigu County, with the aim of constructing a system of Yi ritual music and sorting out the chanting of the Yi people.

Firstly, from a theoretical point of view, this study helps to uncover the 'hidden history' of Yi Bimo music culture. Compared to the mainstream, all intangible cultural heritage, including folk music, has been regarded as a folk tradition and cultural form, and their history is a 'hidden history' compared to that of the mainstream. Historians have long called for a radical shift away from the traditional historiographical view of elite history, which focuses only on the mainstream of society, and towards a focus on the historical status of ordinary people and the writing of histories about them, and the study of Yi Bimo ritual music alludes to this shift in historical research focus. In a sense, the study of Yi Bimo ritual music offers the possibility of uncovering the 'hidden history' of non-mainstream folk cultural groups.

Secondly, in terms of practical application, this study helps to fill the gaps in the existing literature on the study of Yi Bimo music and culture. As carriers of living culture, Yi Bimo bearers rarely take the initiative to record in writing their life history, their artistic career, and the origins, development and evolution of their art and its related culture, and the musical culture they carry is mainly passed on from generation to generation through 'oral tradition'. It is for this reason that the study of Yi bi-mo music should be an important way of collecting and preserving primary sources of Yi folk music culture. The study of this paper will, to a certain extent, contribute to the transmission and development of the ritual music of the Yi people of Liangshan, to the restoration of the social history and traditional music culture of the Yi people of Liangshan, to the study of Yi religious music, and to the progress of the transmission of traditional ethnic culture and the construction of a new culture in the Yi region of Liangshan.

Innovation points of this study

Innovation in research thinking

The main idea of this research is to focus on the musical ontology of the Yi Yi rituals in Liangshan, and on this basis to try to explore and study the cultural context in which the musical ontology was generated and survived. In particular, the research focuses on four aspects: firstly, the study and analysis of musical forms such

as key, tonality, ritual structure, tonal organisation, melodic development, rhythm and meter; secondly, the study and analysis of the types of music used in the rituals of the Bimo in Meigu County, Liangshan Prefecture, in order to accurately grasp the occasions in which Bimo ritual music is used, and to closely connect ritual music with Yi culture; and thirdly, the study and analysis of the Bimo ritual music of The study also aims to analyse the musical forms of the Bimo ritual music of Liangshan, both large and small, in order to identify the cultural origins of the differences. Finally, the essence of the study is to return to the development of musical culture and ecology, which is related to the sound of the Bi'mo rituals of the Liangshan Yi people in the context of modern civilisation, and is a common problem that needs to be solved in the development of Chinese folk music today. With these research concepts in mind, how to enhance the adaptability of ethnic music to ethnic culture and improve cultural confidence and centripetal force are the innovative points of this paper's research ideas.

Innovation in research perspectives

This project focuses on the Bi'mo rituals of the Meigu County of the Liangshan Yi ethnic group, and systematically analyses the Bi'mo rituals of the Liangshan Yi ethnic group in terms of their tonal organisation, tuning and ritual structure, exploring their unique formative factors, distilling their essence and summarising their development patterns. From the study of Yi Bimo ritual music, we delve into the history of the origin of the Yi people, their production, natural environment, family structure, social customs and religious beliefs, and explore the prospects for the development and preservation of traditional ritual music. In addition, the ritual music of the Yi people of Meigu County is representative of the music of the Yi people of Daliang Shan, and a comparison between it and the ritual music of the Yi people of Xiaoliang Shan will yield stylistic differences in the ritual music of the Yi people. Through the above comprehensive fieldwork, the Yi Bimo ritual music was collected, recorded and collated and studied, and a research text on the Yi Bimo ritual music of Meigu County was written to enrich the current research results on Yi Bimo music in general.

Innovation in research methodology

On the basis of the inheritance of previous research results, this paper adopts the theoretical and analytical methods of ethnomusicology and music anthropology to comprehensively examine the music of the Yi Bimo rituals of the Meigu County in Liangshan, summarising the musical characteristics, functions, relevant structural rules and regulations, fixed and non-fixed elements, the relationship with the religious beliefs of the ethnic group and the region, as well as the relationship with other Yi folk music. The study of rituals and other musical matters of the Liangshan Yi ethnic group is carried out in the context of their cultural ecology, and the relationship between the cultural ecology and musical forms is explained, forming a multidisciplinary and multi-layered research approach. In addition, the research results will be deepened, and the original materials collected, such as audio, video and pictures, will be collated and categorised, and technically processed to form a "database of music materials on the Yi rituals of the Liangshan Yi people", which will be submitted to the local cultural authorities for preservation and use.

Theoretical framework construction

This paper focuses on the analysis of a survey report on the ancestor worship and funeral rituals of the Bi Mo in Meigu County, and concludes with a summary of the characteristics of musical behaviour in the Yi ancestor worship rituals. The construction of the Yi Meigu County Bi'mo music system includes two sections: the funeral ritual music system and Bi'mo chanting. The Bi'mo chanting cadences will be categorised and summarised according to the different scriptures that Bi'mo chant in different rituals, in which Bi'mo chanting cannot be separated from the ritual occasions in which it is applied. The article focuses on the study of Yi Bimo ritual music from an anthropological perspective, and will use anthropological methodology to explain the relationship between Yi Bimo ritual music and Yi culture. Based on the results of the previous phase of research, the article will use diverse perspectives to interpret the Bimo ritual music system from sociological, anthropological and psychological perspectives, using the ethnomusicological morphology of In this study, we use the "five states, four paths and three lines" of ethnomusicology to analyse the characteristics of Yi ritual music in the same dialect area that account for its variation.

Conclusion

The religious rituals and funeral ceremonies of the Yi people in Liangshan are mainly conducted by 'bimo' and 'suni', who use their skills to invoke spirits, exorcise ghosts and heal the Yi people. This paper will focus on the music of Bimo rituals, which are mainly hereditary in the family and clan, and on the ritual and musical ontology of sending spirits, making sacrifices, shouting at ghosts and sending them away in rituals and funeral ceremonies.

The first chapter is an analysis of the current state of research on the music of the Yi Yi rituals in Liangshan. On this basis, the second chapter compares the cultural background of the Yi Yi rituals in Liangshan, aiming to provide a comprehensive and in-depth study of the ecological environment of the Yi rituals in Liangshan. The third chapter will combine historical and archaeological research methods to collate the human history, geography and social patterns of Meigu County, the 'hometown of Yi Bimo culture'. Chapter 4 begins with a musicological study of the Yi Bimo rituals in Meigu County, identifying the functions of the Yi Bimo rituals

and providing an in-depth musical and cultural analysis of the preparation and progression of the rituals, with a focus on the Yi Bimo rituals and funeral rituals in Liangshan, analysing the musical and behavioural characteristics of these two rituals. Finally, the social efficacy of Bimo rituals is summarised in terms of the economic and cultural benefits of the musical transmission of Yi Bimo rituals and their cohesive and harmonising effect on family branches.

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